

Robust design method of TMDs for a gable roof subjected to variation in the natural frequency and damping values

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Abstract

TMDs for spatial structures require a different design method than that for multi-story buildings because in spatial structures, multiple modes with close natural frequencies are excited, and their vibration shapes are complex. We have conducted the shaking table test to verify the vibration control effect of TMDs using a scaled-down model of a gable roof (S. Yoshinaka et al. [5]). In this experiment, we simulated damage to the column bases and compared responses by degree of damage. The results show that when seriously damaged, decrease of the natural frequency of the specimen causes TMDs to become ineffective and the responses are amplified because of the weight of the TMD devices. In addition, the vibration control effect seems to depend on the vibration characteristics of the TMD devices. Specifically, the friction of the guide roller can cause amplitude dependence of the damping values. In this paper, we propose a robust design method of TMDs with high robustness against variation in the natural frequency of the specimen and the damping values of the TMD devices. We study highly robust TMDs installation case against the natural frequency decrease, followed by search for cases which are robust against the damping values variation in those cases. Our analysis shows that the method of installing two TMDs, one tuned to the natural frequency of the controlled mode and the other to 30% smaller frequency, is effective for the natural frequency decrease. For the damping values variation, increasing the number of TMDs can lead to higher robustness. Thus, we conclude that the method of installing multiple TMDs with different frequencies is effective for both of those variations.

Keywords: Vibration control, Gable roof, Tuned mass damper, Shaking table test, Scaled-down model, Robust design, Friction force

1. Introduction

TMD (Tuned Mass Damper) is a passive vibration control device consisting of a mass, spring, and damper, primarily applied to multi-story buildings to reduce dynamic responses induced by seismic excitation or strong winds. The high installation flexibility of TMDs on structures, due to its single point of support, can offer its high applicability to spatial structures such as gymnasiums and stadiums. However, TMDs for spatial structures require a different design method than those for multi-story buildings because in spatial structures, multiple modes with close natural frequencies are excited, and their vibration shapes are complex. S. Yoshinaka and K. Kawaguchi have proposed spatially distributed MTMDs (Multiple TMDs) to control multiple modes with close natural frequencies in spatial structures using MTMD method to determine the design parameters of TMDs and have confirmed the vibration control effect through analysis and small-scale model experiments (S. Yoshinaka and K. Kawaguchi [6]).

We have conducted the shaking table test to verify the vibration control effect of TMDs using a scaled-down model of a gable roof (S. Yoshinaka et al. [5]). In this experiment, we simulated damage to the column bases and compared the responses by degree of damage. The results show that when the specimen is seriously damaged, the decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen causes a significant reduction in the vibration control effect of TMDs. In addition, the effect seems to depend on the vibration characteristics of the TMD devices. Specifically, the friction of the guide roller can cause amplitude dependence of the damping values, which was not anticipated during the fabrication of the TMD devices. The effect of conventional TMDs is highly sensitive to variations in the tuning ratio and damping ratio. For example, if the tuning ratio differs by 5% from the optimal value, the effect is reduced by about 50% (H. Yamaguchi [2]). In this paper, we propose a robust design method of TMDs with high robustness against variation in the natural frequency of the specimen and the damping values of TMDs.

2. Experiment overview

In this chapter, the outline of the shaking table test is summarized. Details of the experiment are provided in the reference (S. Yoshinaka et al. [5]).

2.1. Test specimen and TMD devices

The test specimen was a 1/4 scale model of the full-scale gable roof where the shaking table test had been conducted at NIED E-Defense in 2014 (J. Fujiwara et al. [3]). It had a beam span of 5m, a girder span of 2m, column height of 1.75m, and a roof slope of 10:3 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Test specimen

This experiment used two TMDs with different design parameters. The total mass ratio of two TMDs to the weight of the specimen was approximately 5%. The mass of the weights of two TMDs was 31kg each. The tuning ratios and damping ratios were determined by the double dynamic absorber method (K. Seto [4]). The fabricated TMDs have a wider natural frequency range to enhance their robustness. The natural frequencies of each TMD were 4.11 Hz (TMD 1) and 5.21Hz (TMD 2). Air dampers were used because no generic oil dampers that matched optimal damping values were available. Figure 2 shows the free vibration response curve of TMD 2 alone. Friction of the guide roller to fix the vibration direction causes damping without the damper. It also causes amplitude dependence in the damping ratio of the TMD device, with the damping ratio decreasing as the amplitude increases. This is because the frictional force remains constant regardless of the relative velocity, which means that as the velocity increases, resulting in an increase in amplitude, the calculated damping ratio decreases. The vibration characteristics of the TMD devices are described in detail in Section 4.

Figure 2: Free vibration response curves (TMD 2)

2.2. Experimental procedure

The experimental conditions include three cases each for column base damage and TMD installation. The column base damage was simulated by removing the splice plates (Figure 3). Figure 4 displays the damage cases, with the columns indicated by the red circles as the damaged locations. Table 1 shows the TMD installation cases. Figure 5 is the modal shape of the 1st mode, which is the control mode. The installation position of the TMD devices on the roof is indicated by the red circle among the four circles representing the nodes of the 1st mode. The installation positions were determined considering the symmetry of the specimen. The installation position in Case 3 is on the side of the top of the column (Figure 6). Figure 7 illustrates the experiment in Case 1. The column bases were fixed by foundation beams because the span of the specimen was larger than the size of the shaking table.

Figure 3: Column base damage simulation

Figure 4: Column base damage cases

Table 1: TMD installation cases

	Position	Direction of TMD vibration
Case1	Roof	1st mode
Case2	Roof	Horizontal
Case3	Top of column	Horizontal

Figure 5: 1st modal shape

Figure 6: Installed TMD (Case 3)

Figure 7: Shaking table test

2.3. Test results

Table 2 compares the maximum values and RMS (Root Mean Square) values of the horizontal displacements at the top of the column in each case when excited by a simulated earthquake ground motion of JSCA (Japan Structural Consultants Association). Case 0 in Table 2 represents a case with no TMD. In the case with all the columns damaged, both the maximum values and RMS values increase compared to the undamaged case. The reason is that decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen causes TMDs to become ineffective and the responses are amplified seemingly because of the weight of the TMD devices. Table 3 shows the maximum values and RMS values of the horizontal displacements of the TMD devices and the mass ratio of the TMDs, calculated using the equivalent

mass of the 1st mode at the installation locations of the TMDs and the total mass of the TMD devices, 62kg. No significant differences in the vibration control effect in each TMD installation case are observed, especially in the undamaged case. The possible reason is that in Case 1 and Case 2, with a higher mass ratio compared to Case 3, the amplitude of the device is larger, which leads to a decrease in the damping values of the TMDs due to the amplitude dependence of the TMD devices.

Table 2: Displacements in each case

	Maximum displacement (mm)			RMS value (mm)		
	Undamaged	Half of columns damaged	All columns damaged	Undamaged	Half of columns damaged	All columns damaged
Case0	3.47	5.99	8.50	0.997	1.171	2.714
Case1	3.05	5.71	11.32	0.528	1.147	2.753
Case2	2.78	5.11	12.98	0.542	1.179	3.235
Case3	2.84	4.04	13.27	0.551	1.108	3.246

Table 3: Mass ratio, displacements of TMDs

	Mass ratio	Maximum displacement (mm)		RMS value (mm)	
		TMD1	TMD2	TMD1	TMD2
Case1	0.0612	23.18	10.32	4.50	1.50
Case2	0.0510	23.29	10.12	4.17	1.38
Case3	0.0364	19.07	8.39	3.33	1.43

3. Robust design against decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen

In this chapter, we present the robust design for TMDs to achieve sufficient performance even if the specimen damage causes decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen.

3.1. Robust design

This study employed a method to install multiple TMDs with different natural frequencies. The cases of 1 to 4 TMDs are considered. One of them was tuned to the natural frequency of the undamaged specimen to ensure the vibration control effect in the undamaged case, and the others were tuned to the frequencies reduced by a certain ratio to deal with the decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen. The natural frequencies of the 1st mode in each damage case obtained from the Fourier spectrum are 4.615 Hz in the undamaged case (reduction rate: 0%), 4.000 Hz in the case with half of the columns damaged (reduction rate: approximately 13%), 3.307 Hz in the case with all the columns damaged (reduction rate: approximately 28%). Based on this, the tuned frequencies were set as shown in Table 4. The parameters of each TMD were calculated using Equation (1) and (2), optimal parameters for harmonic ground motion (G. B. Warburton [1]). μ , γ_{opt} , and ξ_{opt} represent the mass ratio, optimal tuning ratio, and optimal damping ratio respectively. The total mass ratio is set to approximately 5% regardless of the number of TMDs.

$$\gamma_{opt} = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \mu/2}}{1 + \mu} \tag{1}$$

$$\xi_{opt} = \sqrt{\frac{3\mu}{8(1 + \mu)(1 - \mu/2)}} \tag{2}$$

Table 4: TMD tuned frequencies

TMD	Reduction rate of frequency	Tuned frequency (Hz)
o	0%	4.615
a	7.5%	4.269
b	15%	3.923
c	22.5%	3.577
d	30%	3.231

3.2. Analytical model

The analysis used a model similar to the one in the experiment, utilizing Simcenter Femap with Nastran for FEM (Finite Element Method). The columns and girders were modeled with beam elements, while the beams and small beams and braces were modeled using rod elements. The column base was fixed. The Young's modulus of the material was modified to match to the natural frequency of the 1st mode of the specimen in the experiment.

3.3. Analytical method

A linear time history response analysis was performed. The analysis conditions include three cases for column base damage and 16 cases for TMD installation. The damage cases are identical as those in the experiment. The damage was simulated by replacing the beam elements at the damaged location with beam elements having a rectangular cross-section equivalent to the cross-sectional area of two splice plates, and the Young's modulus was adjusted to correspond to the natural frequency shown in Section 3.1. The vibration direction of the device was limited to Case 2 in Table 1. Table 5 and Figure 8 show TMD installation cases and installation positions, respectively. The total mass of the TMDs was 62kg regardless of the number of TMDs. The damping of the specimen was modeled using Rayleigh damping, with 1% damping ratio for the 1st and 4th modes, where the effective mass ratio was high in the undamaged case. The relationship between the change in mode shapes due to the column base damage and the TMD installation positions was not considered.

Table 5: TMD installation cases

Case No.	Number of TMDs	TMD installed
0	0TMD	—
1	1TMD	o
2	2TMD	o,a
3		o,b
4		o,c
5		o,d
6	3TMD	o,a,b
7		o,a,c
8		o,a,d
9		o,b,c
10		o,b,d
11	o,c,d	
12	4TMD	o,a,b,c
13		o,a,b,d
14		o,a,c,d
15		o,b,c,d

Figure 8: TMD installation positions

3.4. Analytical results

3.4.1. Comparison of the vibration control effects based on TMDs parameters

Figure 9 shows the maximum values and RMS values of the horizontal displacements at the top of the column in the cases with two TMDs (Case 2 - Case 5 in Table 5) when excited by the JSCA wave. For comparison, the case with no TMD is referred to as Case 0. The difference between TMD installation cases is small in the undamaged case and the case with half of the columns damaged, but becomes significant in the case with all the columns damaged. The case using TMD-d, which is tuned to the natural frequency in the case with all the columns damaged (Case 5), results in the highest vibration control effect. This trend is also observed in the case with different number of TMDs. The reason for the effect in Case 5 being maintained in the case with half of the columns damaged can be attributed to the characteristic of TMDs that the decrease in the effect is smaller when the natural frequency of the specimen is higher than the tuned frequency of TMDs compared to when the natural frequency of the specimen is lower (S. Yoshinaka [7]).

Figure 9: Displacements in each damage case

3.4.2. Comparison of the vibration control effects based on numbers of TMDs

Figure 10 shows the maximum values and RMS values of the horizontal displacements at the top of the column in the cases with the smallest response for each number of TMDs. The numbers following Case No. in the legend of the figure indicate the number of TMDs. Installing multiple TMDs exhibits the higher vibration control effect compared to a single TMD, and the effect is higher with two TMDs than with three or four TMDs. As in the previous section, the larger mass of TMD-d apparently results in the higher effect. Thus, our analysis shows that the method of installing two TMDs, one tuned to the natural frequency of the controlled mode and the other tuned to 30% smaller frequency, is effective for the natural frequency decrease in this specimen.

Figure 10: Displacements in each damage case

4. Damping characteristics of TMD devices

In this chapter, we report the results of studies on the damping characteristics of TMD devices. Figure 11 displays the TMD device. As in Section 2.1, the damping value of the TMD device depends on the frictional force of the guide roller to fix the vibration direction and the viscous damping of the air damper.

Figure 11: TMD device

4.1. Estimation of the damping value of the TMD device

4.1.1. Frictional force

We estimated the frictional force from the results of the free vibration test with the air damper valve fully open. The response curve was calculated using the equation of motion shown in Equation (3) (JSME, [8]). F_c in the equation represents the frictional force. The frictional force was calculated to be 8.655N using the method of derived from the difference in peak amplitudes of the response curve (JSME, [8]). Figure 12 compares the test result and the response curve obtained by analysis with the calculated frictional force. The test result broadly corresponds to the analytical result, but slight differences are observed in the small amplitude range.

$$m\ddot{x}(t) + kx(t) = -F_c \operatorname{sgn}(\dot{x}) = \begin{cases} -F_c & ; \dot{x} > 0 \\ +F_c & ; \dot{x} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

4.1.2. Viscous damping

Subsequently, we estimated the viscous damping coefficient from the results of the free vibration test with the air damper valve closed, the state where both frictional force and viscous damping work. The response curve was calculated using the equation of motion shown in Equation (4) (JSME, [9]). Figure 13 compares the test result with the analytical result. The damping ratio was determined to match the second amplitude peak in Figure 13, resulting in a damping ratio of 0.0291. The test result broadly corresponds to the analytical result, but slight differences are observed in the small amplitude range.

$$m\ddot{x}(t) + c\dot{x}(t) + kx(t) = -F_c \operatorname{sgn}(\dot{x}) = \begin{cases} -F_c & ; \dot{x} > 0 \\ +F_c & ; \dot{x} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 12: Response curves without damper

Figure 13: Response curves with damper

4.2. Vibration characteristics of the TMD device

We conducted the shaking table test with the TMD device alone. We outline the experiment and study the vibration characteristics of the TMD devices through analysis. Details of the experiment are provided in the reference (S. Yoshinaka et al. [5]).

We conducted the sweep excitation test with the TMD device alone to obtain the frequency response. The experimental conditions include three cases for the installation angles of the device and two cases for the excitation amplitudes. The installation angles were 0 degrees, 15 degrees, and 40 degrees. The excitation amplitudes were $\pm 0.75\text{mm}$ and $\pm 1.5\text{mm}$. Figure 14 illustrates the experiment in the case of the installation angle of 40 degrees. Additionally, we performed harmonic vibration analysis using the frictional force and damping ratio mentioned in the previous section to obtain the frequency response. Table 6 compares the test result and the analytical result of the maximum frequency responses. The results are approximately the same for both 0 degrees and 40 degrees. In the case of 15 degrees, the test response was larger; therefore, by considering the amplitude dependence and reducing the frictional force and damping ratio by 0.8 each (frictional force: 6.924N, damping ratio: 0.0233), the analytical results, which are almost identical to the test results, were obtained, as shown in parentheses in Table 6. In systems where the influence of friction is significant, the frequency response depends on the excitation amplitude (Z. Gewei and B. Basu, [10]), as observed in the results.

Figure 14: Shaking table test with the TMD device alone

Table 6: Maximum frequency responses

Angle	Amplitude $\pm 0.75\text{mm}$		Amplitude $\pm 1.5\text{mm}$	
	Experiment	Analysis	Experiment	Analysis
0°	9.56	9.06	14.65	13.01
15°	13.52	8.74 (12.63)	16.01	12.56 (16.40)
40°	7.84	6.93	10.48	9.96

5. Robust design against variation in the natural frequency and damping values

In this chapter, we propose a robust design that accounts for variation in both the tuning ratios and damping values by adopting a method for installing TMDs with high robustness against the decrease in the natural frequency of the specimen as described in Section 3 and verifying the stability of the vibration control effect to variation in the damping values of TMDs.

5.1. Setting of tuned frequencies

The tuned frequencies of TMDs were adopted from the cases confirmed to be robust against the decrease in the natural frequency in Section 3.4. Viscous damping was considered exclusively for damping values.

5.2. Analytical method

The analysis used a model similar to the one in Section 3.2 (the undamaged case) and conducted a linear time history analysis. Regarding the number of TMDs and the tuned frequencies, we adopted Case 5, Case 11, and Case 15 in Table 5, which exhibited high robustness against the decrease in the

natural frequency for installation numbers ranging from 2 to 4. We also used Case 1, which showed lower robustness with one TMD for comparison. We varied the damping ratios from 0.05 to 0.15 in increments of 0.01 and compared the maximum values and RMS values of the horizontal displacements at the top of the column. The vibration direction of the device was limited to Case 2 in Table 1. The TMD installation positions were the same as those shown in Figure 8. The total mass of TMDs was 62kg regardless of the number of TMDs.

5.3. Analytical results

Figure 15 shows the maximum values and RMS values of the horizontal displacements at the top of the column when excited by the JSCA wave. The number in front of TMD in the legend of the figure indicates the number of TMDs. The results show that increasing the number of TMDs leads to smaller changes in both the maximum values and the RMS values to variations in the damping values. This is seemingly because within the same TMD natural frequency bandwidth from TMD-o to TMD-d in Table 4, a larger number of TMDs causes more peaks in the frequency response curve. The greater response with larger numbers of TMDs can be attributed to the reason that the mass of the TMD that is tuned to the natural frequency of the first mode in the undamaged case is greater when the number of TMDs is smaller. Thus, installing a single TMD results in a high vibration control effect, but as mentioned, has lower robustness against variations in the damping values. Overall, Case 5, Case 11, and Case 15, which use multiple TMDs, exhibit high robustness against variation in the damping values in this specimen.

Figure 15: Displacements in each damping value

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we studied the robust design of TMDs against variation in both the natural frequency of the test specimen and the damping values of TMDs through analysis based on results of a shaking table test to verify the effect of TMDs for a gable roof using a scaled-down specimen. We summarize the findings obtained below.

- (1) The method of installing two TMDs, one tuned to the natural frequency of the controlled mode and the other tuned to 30% smaller frequency, is effective for the natural frequency decrease.
- (2) The TMD devices used in the experiment are strongly influenced by the friction of the guide roller, exhibiting amplitude dependence where the calculated damping ratio decreases as the amplitude increases, showing a different response characteristic with respect to the excitation amplitude.
- (3) Increasing the number of TMDs can lead to higher robustness to the variation of the damping values variation.
- (4) The method of installing multiple TMDs including the one tuned to the natural frequency of the controlled mode and the one to 30% smaller frequency is robust against variation in both the tuning ratios and damping values.

Figure 16 shows the procedure for designing TMDs with high robustness against variation in the natural frequency of structures and damping values of TMDs based on this study.

Figure 16: Procedure for designing TMDs

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